

THE ROLE OF DATA SHARING AGREEMENTS TO ENHANCE
CONFIDENTIALITY IN DATA SHARING PROCESS

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Abstract

With the increasing prominence of data-driven initiatives and the need for effective collaboration between entities, understanding the legal framework governing data sharing becomes paramount. The thesis explores the theoretical considerations surrounding data sharing agreements, key aspects of this process such as consent, data protection, liability, and confidentiality. By delving into the intricacies of data sharing arrangements, this paper aims to assist organizations in navigating the complex legal landscape, ensuring compliance, and fostering successful partnerships in the realm of data sharing.

Keywords: data sharing, data sharing agreements, protection of individual rights, law.

Data sharing agreements play a critical role in the modern digital world, where the exchange and utilization of data have become essential for various sectors, including business, research, and government. The rapid advancement of technology and the exponential growth of data have posed unique legal challenges in the context of data sharing agreements. Successful data sharing has become an essential component of effective collaboration among organizations. Data sharing helps unlock valuable insights and enables businesses to make informed decisions, drive innovation, and achieve competitive advantages. However, realizing the full potential of data sharing requires a clear understanding of its importance and adherence to key guidelines for effective collaboration [1]. In order to clear

understanding the nature of data sharing agreements, it is necessary to know what is the process is data sharing. Data sharing refers to the act of letting another party use data. It has become prevalent with the spread of internet technologies such as email, websites and P2P systems [2]. However, data sharing process not only involves the data exchange, it is only part of this process, but data sharing is making the same data available to other users. In this process raw data can be processed, transferred, amended and finalized by many users at the same time. And this process is not only the opportunity to process data in collaboration, for ex. In research works, business projects or even in drafting legal documents, it can be a reason for disputes and conflicts regarding the usage of data, since it can be sensitive data. To resolve these issues several ways offered by the representatives of the sphere. And data sharing agreements are considered one of these solutions. Data sharing agreements set out the purpose of the data sharing, cover what happens to the data at each stage, set standards and help all the parties involved in sharing to be clear about their roles and responsibilities [3].

Health care organizations participating in health information exchange initiatives develop and codify their data governance policies in a variety of legal documents, collectively known as data sharing agreements (DSAs) [4]. Data sharing clauses are usually specified in legal documents that are far from being amenable of automated processing by the electronic platform that should enforce them. Furthermore, different parties usually pursue different interests. This may lead to conflicts that need to be solved for the agreements to succeed [5]. However, in practice, we may face different types of agreements that used in sphere of data sharing, but they do not cover the same objects as data sharing agreements. Some common types of DSAs include Data Use Agreements (DUA), Business Associate Agreements (BAA), and Participation Agreements (PA) [6].

Data Use Agreements mainly used to define the data that may be used or disclosed by the entity. Business Associate Agreement is an document concluded

between the persons or entities that performs certain functions or activities involving the use or disclosure of protected health information on behalf of, or provides services to, a covered entity. Data Use and reciprocal Support Agreement is a multi-party trust agreement that is entered into voluntarily by every entity. Participation Agreement is designed to ensure that participants comply with the data sharing policies and procedures.

Data sharing agreements encompass several legal aspects that ensure the protection, privacy, and compliance of shared data:

1. **Data Protection and Privacy:** Compliance with relevant data protection laws (e.g., GDPR, CCPA) is crucial. Agreements should specify the lawful basis for data processing, consent requirements, and limitations on data use and disclosure.

2. **Confidentiality and Security:** The agreement must address data confidentiality and security measures to safeguard against unauthorized access, disclosure, or loss. It should outline technical and organizational safeguards, incident response procedures, and data breach notification requirements.

3. **Ownership and Intellectual Property:** Clear provisions should define ownership rights and intellectual property considerations for shared data. Parties must clarify whether shared data retains its original owners, or if it becomes jointly owned or subject to licensing terms.

4. **Compliance with Industry Regulations:** Depending on the sector, specific regulations (e.g., HIPAA for healthcare data) may impose additional requirements for data sharing agreements, such as audit trails, data retention, or special safeguards for sensitive information.

5. **Data Transfer Mechanisms:** If data is transferred across borders, the agreement should address international data transfers and comply with applicable cross-border data transfer mechanisms, such as the EU Standard Contractual Clauses or Binding Corporate Rules.

6. Liability and Indemnification: The agreement should allocate liability for data breaches or non-compliance, define indemnification obligations, and outline remedies or dispute resolution procedures.

7. Data Retention and Deletion: Clear guidelines on data retention periods, data disposal, and the return or destruction of shared data at the end of the agreement should be included.

8. Audit and Monitoring Rights: The agreement may grant audit and monitoring rights to ensure compliance with the terms, including periodic assessments of data handling practices or security audits.

References:

1. Ghosh P., What Are Data Sharing Agreements and Why Are They Important? November 9, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://www.dataiversity.net/what-are-data-sharing-agreements-and-why-are-they-important/#:~:text=Legal%20Requirements%20and%20Confidentiality&text=These%20conditions%20often%20include%20obtaining,aspect%20of%20data%20sharing%20agreements.>
2. Swarup V., Seligman L. and Rosenthal A. A Data Sharing Agreement Framework. The MITRE Cooperation 7515 Colshire Drive McLean, VA 22102. Conference paper pp 22-36 Retrieved from: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/11961635_2
3. Data sharing agreements – Information Commissioner’s Office. Retrieved from: [https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-sharing/data-sharing-a-code-of-practice/data-sharing-agreements/?q=security.](https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-sharing/data-sharing-a-code-of-practice/data-sharing-agreements/?q=security)
4. Middleton B, Fleming M, Wiegand T, Merritt D, Bakalar R, Georgiou A, Marchibroda J, Whitlinger D, Davidson G, Schlaifer D. Best

Practices for Community Health Information Exchange. *Center for Community Health Leadership*. 2013 [[Google Scholar](#)]

5. Egea M., Matteucci I. Definition of Data Sharing Agreements april 2015, *Accountability and Security in the Cloud* (pp. 248-272) DOI:[10.1007/978-3-319-17199-9_11](#). Retrieved from:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/312828364_Definition_of_Data_Sharing_Agreements

6. Allen C., and other. Data Governance and Data Sharing Agreements for Community-Wide Health Information Exchange: Lessons from the Beacon Communities [EGEMS \(Wash DC\)](#). 2014; 2(1): 1057. Published online 2014 Apr 23. doi: [10.13063/2327-9214.1057](#) Retrieved from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4371395/#b4-egems1057>